

IMPACT OF DAYLIGHTING AND
FENESTRATION ON SCHOOL BUILDING
DESIGN, ILAJE COMMUNITY, LAGOS
STATE.

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF
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THE AWARD OF BACHELORS OF SCIENCE (BSc) DEGREE IN ARCHITECTURE.

BY

MOMODU DAVID

170501507

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this thesis “**Impact Of Daylighting And Fenestration In School Building Design, Ilaje Community, Lagos State**” with matriculation number, **170501507** of the Department of Architecture, University of Lagos, is an original work and meets the regulations governing the award of Bachelor of science (BSc) degree in architecture, and is approved for its contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

Dr. Yemi Oginni
Supervisor

Dr. Anthony Iweka
Head of Department

DECLARATION

I **MOMODU, DAVID EWELA** with the matriculation number, **170501507** declare this design thesis titled “**IMPACT OF DAYLIGHTING AND FENESTRATION IN SCHOOL BUILDING DESIGN, ILAJE COMMUNITY**” under the supervision of Dr. Yemi Oginni and has been done by myself and ensure that this thesis has never been presented elsewhere.

MOMODU E. DAVID

DATE

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ABSTRACT

The study of daylight conditions and fenestration within educational buildings has been a topic of interest among architects as a means to improve schooling experience. Although it has been argued that providing a view outside—or even using daylight instead of more stable and manageable artificial light—could reduce students’ performance without providing a pleasant and healthy environment, nowadays there is a large consensus upon the need to design well day lit spaces is being reached. A well-lit space is one of the important environmental factors that affect the health, emotions and academic performance of the students. The methodology used depended on data collection from various case studies, and analysis of design information obtained from architectural drawings of standard schools, design compliance documents set by the relevant governmental bodies, **Universal Basic Education** Commission of Nigeria (**UBE**), site visits and photography. It analyzed several important design issues that have significant impact on several independent factors such as visual and thermal quality, including space size and depth to height ratio, windows orientation, lighting direction and desk position. It also investigate potential problems during critical times and view angles.

Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Daylight and sunlight in classrooms have been utilized as a design element in educational buildings in recent years. One of the main reasons for using daylight in recent years is its benefit in reducing energy consumption through its use as a main or secondary illumination source in order to replace the use of electrical lighting, but most importantly, it has shown that such design element are closely related to issues like human performance. Reasons for utilizing daylight may vary from one designer to another. One main reason for using daylight is its physiological and psychological impact on student. According to some researchers, Daryanani (1), the most important benefit from the application of daylighting in a public building is not energy conservation, but increased occupant satisfaction. Collins (2), in a study of the psychological reaction to windows, indicates the basic need for a window as a medium of contact with the outside for human beings. In addition to physiological benefits, natural illumination in the form of both daylight and sunshine adds desirable psychological qualities to an interior environment other psychological and physiological benefits resulting from the admission of daylight are the feeling of spaciousness which daylight adds to the room. According to **UBE** Commission of Nigeria (3), a sense of orientation within the surroundings, and connection with external weather and climate conditions. These valuable effects make these design elements (daylight and fenestration) an aesthetic tool for the architect and an asset for the users of the building.

To achieve a proper orientation that utilizes weather and climate conditions, various considerations are observed. Such as, operation period (or occupancy period — for schools in Lagos it is usually between September to June, that is, the cooler dry season (accompanied by Harmattan winds from Sahara desert), and rainy season, with only 30 days approximately for the summer season. This gives priority need for proper shading devices. It should also be noted that among prevailing wind directions for the Ilaje region such as Tropical Continental Air mass and Tropical Maritime Air mass, there is also the Southeast sea breeze from the lagoon. Other considerations such as; Sun path and Wind Direction—The placement of the building on the site and arrangement of spaces and openings— Large openings would not face directly to the East and West as to avoid direct sunlight and concentration of heat. The lesser surface area / or building facade exposed to the sun, lesser will be the conductive heating— Placing openings parallel to the wind orientation to create a cool interior—Use of wind direction so that it can be channelized through the interiors— Consider the placement & size of openings for optimum ventilation.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The assessment of a building orientation and performance amounts to several benefits of which visual comfort of student is key. This study looks at the effect of daylighting in school building, conducted to optimize the façade design of a typical school regarding the daylight through the comparison of the different fenestration configurations for different orientations in a specific climatic condition. This study looks at how daylighting, from windows or skylights, influence students. To assess known problems and to explore the effect

of orientation; the effect of area, shape and position of the windows; on daylight and thermal performance and comfort conditions. – to determine the better fenestration configurations for different orientations in terms of their relative performance - to understand the relation between classroom size, classroom ventilation, poor lighting in classroom of alternative fenestration compositions, to analyze the reasons of visual discomfort conditions with respect to design criteria.

1.3 AIMS & OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

AIM

The aim of this study is to optimize certain design elements of typical school regarding the daylight and thermal performance through the comparison of the different fenestration configurations for different orientations in a specific climatic condition and the use of natural daylighting for better performance and visual comfort of student. This shall cumulate in the design of a leaning environment in an urban area for students receiving secondary education.

OBJECTIVES

The fundamental objectives of the study are;

- To explore the effect of orientation; area, shape and position of the windows; on daylight and thermal performance and comfort conditions.
- To determine the better fenestration configurations for different orientations in terms of their relative performance

- To understand the relation between daylight and thermal performance of alternative fenestration compositions.
- To analyze the reasons of visual and thermal discomfort conditions with respect to design criteria and present some of the general considerations which must be met as well as some of the pitfalls to be avoided.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What are the impacts of daylighting and fenestration configurations on school building?
- How weather and climate conditions of a region influence design elements in a building?
- How orientation design consideration influence student satisfaction?
- How mitigate negative effects that may stem from the oversupply of daylight such as glare risks, room overheating and lack of privacy

1.5 SCOPE OF STUDY

Ilaje- bariga is a slum settlement within the Bariga community of Shomolu local government area in Lagos metropolis with features such as unplanned developments and squatter settlements, religious buildings, shops and market sharing common compounds in extremely dense areas. This study's scope includes student's satisfaction, perception, and the importance of a school with emphasis on the utilization of various design elements in a slum area.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The significance of this study is to act as a guiding principle for other designers and architects, to achieve an ideal school design in other slum area around world through proper orientation, and to take this matter out of the realm of mere opinion and base it on fact. From this material a program may be synthesized for a given climate region. For example, two of the many cardinal principles to be observed in school planning are:

- Determine the weather and climate of the location of the school building to be placed;
- Determine toward what direction in which a schoolroom should face— the control of the amount of direct sunlight which will enter the room

No one can intelligently plan a building without this information

1.7 LIMITATION OF STUDY

This study was limited to secondary schools, namely junior secondary school 1 (JSS1) to senior secondary school 3 (SSS3). It was limited to orientation of the school in relation to the regional weather and climate to achieve a desirable daylighting and fenestration configuration. This confined and limited the study to a realistic program and separated it as a part of the larger design elements and guidance objective. The study was concerned with those programs, practices, and techniques, which would aid in the adaptation and adjustment of the student to the school environment.

1.8 DEFINITION OF TERMS

- **A School** – is an educational institution designed to provide learning spaces and learning environments for the teaching of students (or "pupils") under the direction of teachers.

- **A Secondary school** – is an intermediary between elementary/primary school and college and usually offering general, technical, vocational, or college-preparatory courses.
- **Fenestration:**

Fenestration is a term used to describe the arrangement, quality, quantity or aesthetic

Characteristics of the totality of windows on a building's façade.

Fenestration design is fundamentally a problem of optimization. Light admission or solar gain depends considerably on orientation, the area, shape, location and thermal and optical properties of windows

- **Daylighting:**

Daylighting is the controlled admission of natural light, direct sunlight, into a building to reduce electric lighting and saving energy, for efficient visual performance and to ensure a comfortable and pleasing environment appropriate to its purpose.

Chapter 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 DAYLIGHTING.

Natural light was the main source of illumination in buildings before the advent of electricity. It has always played a dominant role in architecture, both to reveal the architecture of the building and to create a particular atmosphere as well as to provide the occupants with visual comfort and functional illumination. The aim of a good daylight design is first to provide sufficient light for efficient visual performance and second to ensure a comfortable and pleasing environment appropriate to its purpose. Thus, not only quantity but also quality of light is important. Baker and Steemers (4) Providing sufficient daylight to buildings can be quite a challenge due to the great variability in available daylight. It can sometimes be less or sometimes be more. Thomas (5), the period of time when daylight is likely to satisfy the lighting needs of a building can be calculated for specific latitude using a set of curves published by the (CIE) Commission international de l'éclairage (fig 1 below). The position of the sun in the sky is often represented on sun path diagrams where the solar altitude and azimuth angles for the whole year, hour by hour are plotted. Sun path diagrams, varying with latitude, composed of series of curves. For specific latitude, each curve represented the sun path of one day and whole curves constitute a year.

2.1.1.1 Direct Sunlight

The amount of sunlight reaching a surface is affected by the geometrical relationship between the sun and the surface. With the exception of the two periods just after sunrise and just before sunset, direct normal illuminance, values do not vary greatly during the hours of a particular day at a given location Hopkinson (6). Direct sunlight in sunny climates is usually high. Illuminance received on the horizontal from sun and sky. This fact illustrates the importance of direct sunlight as a major source of natural light in sunny areas. The direct illuminance reaching the earth is a function of several variables. It is influenced by the location of the sun, the elasticity of the earth's orbit, atmospheric conditions (cloud cover, haze, dust etc.) and the length of the sun path through the atmosphere.

2.1.1.2 Skylight

Cloud cover in tropical arid climates as is the case in Nigeria, is low. It usually covers less than 30% of the sky dome Ander.G.D (7). Under such a sky, sunlight is intercepted by the molecules of the earth's atmosphere causing the wavelengths of light in the blue portion of the spectrum to be scattered, which produces the characteristic blue colour (skylight) of the clear sky Moore (8). The luminance of such a sky is low and may be insufficiently bright to act as a major source of interior illumination. The clear blue sky produces a far from uniform distribution of brightness. The brightest region of the sky is the zone around the sun. The darkest is the region, which is at 90° from the sun in the plane of the solar azimuth, Baker, Fanchiott (9). The luminance distribution of a clear sky changes almost constantly due to the movement of the sun. However, the average luminance of the sky remains fairly constant throughout the day, Hopkinson (6).

2.1.1.3 Daylight Level Metrics.

It is difficult to characterize indoor daylighting because of the numerous design parameters that have to be considered, such as view factor, aperture size, and room depth. Nevertheless, experiments, numerical studies, and simplified procedures are common methods used to determine interior illuminance. Either the daylight illumination in an interior can be described in absolute terms as illumination value or as a percentage in the way of daylight factor; they are regularly used as a guide to adequate daylighting. “In terms of daylighting metrics, daylight factor is the ratio of interior to exterior illuminance over a horizontal plane and has been the dominant metric for daylight design for over 50 years”, Longyu Guan (11). The amount of daylight inside a room can be measured by comparing it with the total daylight available outside the room. This ratio is called daylight factor (DF) which can be measured in percentage (%).

$$DF = \frac{\text{Indoor illuminance from daylight}}{\text{Horizontal unobstructed outdoor illuminance}} \times 100\%$$

In daylight factor concept, the effects of direct and reflected sunlight are excluded. Thus, daylight factor concept is inapplicable in the calculation of the daylight illumination in sunny climates -clear or partly cloudy sky with sunlight, Hopkinson (6)

Fig. 2; Components Comprising Daylight Factor, Heerwagen (10).

2.1.1.4 Elements of Daylighting

Design The penetration, distribution and amount of daylight depends on orientation; space organization, geometry and dimension of spaces; the location, form and dimension of openings; the locations and surface properties of internal partitions; the location, dimension and form of solar control devices; the light and thermal characteristics of glazing materials. Goulding (12) Windows in vertical walls and skylights are conventional openings used in daylighting. In addition to these conventional openings; lightwells or shafts, tubular skylights, heliostats, fiber optics or light pipes can be used in bringing daylight into the interior of buildings. Lechner (13).

2.1.1.5 Daylighting Feasibility

To determine how much daylight you can use in various areas of your building. Because windows are not used simply to illuminate an interior space (e.g., they provide a view, outdoor connection, ventilation), the issue is not whether or not to use a window, but whether one can capitalize on it to increase occupant comfort, satisfaction, and perhaps performance. Determine how much daylight can be used to offset artificial lighting needs.

Day lighting would be effective when daylight falls on windows throughout the day. Higher glazing should provide good day lighting. Orientation, door height, sky views, ground reflectance, and interior design can be treated together for feasibility at each portion of a room. The appropriate choice of glazing in a facade depends on many factors. They include location, orientation, climatic condition, window transmittance, usage of the building, required user comfort.

The Feasibility Factor (FF) is expressed as;

Feasibility = “how much glass” x “how transparent” x “obstructions blocking light”

$$FF = WWR \times WT \times OF$$

The above expression, WWR is window to wall ratio, OF is obstruction factor, and WT is visible window transmittance. For maximum daylight effectiveness, sitting arrangement, fade, and windows play an important role. Light colored surfaces will reflect more daylight than dark surfaces. Spaces with windows on two sides often have better day lighting distribution. If the Feasibility Factor is ≥ 0.25 , then daylighting has the potential for significant energy savings for this building zone. If the Feasibility Factor is < 0.25 , then consider removing obstructions, increasing window area, or increasing visible window transmittance. If these modifications are not possible, it is unlikely that daylighting will be a cost-effective energy-saving strategy, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (14). However, windows can still be designed to provide views and to control glare.

2.1.2 FENESTRATION DESIGN

Fenestration design is fundamentally a problem of optimization. Light admission or solar gain depends considerably on orientation Thomas (5). Fenestration design with respect to sun requires a careful control to maintain the temperature of the room between the comfort limits, to prevent sunlight from directly falling onto occupants, to reduce the illuminance of particular surfaces to avoid glare, to prevent the view of the sun to avoid glare. In addition, avoidance of sky view to prevent glare may also be required. However, in daylighting design, these objectives have to be met without the impairment of the daylighting conditions up to a need for artificial light. Baker and Steemers (4), there is a contradiction in the optimization of window sizes simultaneously for low energy consumption requiring small sizes with high visual comfort requiring large sizes. The area, shape, location and thermal and optical properties of windows

and dimension, type and location of a shading device has a greater influence on the heat loss, heat gain and light admission through windows, Heerwagen (10).

Fenestration design strategies aims to distribute daylight into the depth of a space, to provide enough light to perform a task in the room while avoiding glare and allowing a view to the outside. Facades generally have a limited ability to distribute daylight into the depth of a space. Several rules of thumb apply to potential daylighting zones for diffuse skylight and appropriate window design. During the conceptual design phase, the daylighting zone may be considered to be a depth of about two times the window head height, Robbins (26).

Other fenestration strategies like toplighting can only be used on the top floor of a building. Spaces on lower floors can only be connected to rooflights by core daylighting systems or atria. Rooflights receive light from the brightest regions of the sky, so they are powerful sources of daylight. They do not, however, provide users with a view to the outside, so daylighting strategies that depend exclusively on rooflights are limited to spaces where a view is not necessary. Solar shading is usually essential to prevent overheating because toplighting is exposed to high incident sunlight. The size of rooflights needs to be carefully balanced to meet lighting, thermal performance, and shading requirements. Various rooflighting shading strategies and systems exist.

Rooflights are often glazed with light-diffusing glass to protect the interior from direct sunrays, Light-diffusing glass does not provide solar shading. However, and becomes very bright when hit by direct sunlight, which may cause glare, Herbert M. Eckerlin (25). the ability of facades to distribute daylight to deep spaces is limited, especially under cloudy skies, bilateral and multilateral lighting is an option for rooms that cannot be lit adequately by only one façade. Bilateral daylighting with a functional division between facades is a powerful daylighting

strategy that can be applied in different ways. One way is to allocate the function of view to the outside to one facade using daylighting systems such as overhangs that shade sunlight but do not obstruct the view

2.1.3 WINDOW

For a fixed window height, if the window is placed higher, the daylighting zone is deeper. The typical depth of a day lighted zone is 1.5 to 2 times the head height of window, O Connor & Lee... (15). More control is required for large windows to mitigate the effects of solar heat gain. Similarly, if the glass area is more, then required visible window transmittance reduces. South facing windows provide good access to strong illumination. North facing windows provide quality consistent daylight with minimal heat gains. In case of East and West facing windows, shading is difficult, and hence maximum people choose north or south facing windows. The amount of daylight will vary throughout the day. Integrating personal shading or glare control systems into required spaces, Bodart & Deneyer... (16), are some of the steps to mitigate excessive daylight. Three different sitting arrangements are shown below.

Fig. 3 O Connor & Lee... (15)

Among the three, person sitting as shown in the left side encounters shading on desk, and the person sitting on the right has a tiring effect on eyes due to excessive daylight.

These two positions limit productivity of person. The preferred sitting position is as shown in the middle...

2.1.3.1 Window Orientation

The orientation of a building façade, and hence the windows within it, has an important bearing on the interior environment. There are two important aspects of this: first, the setting of the building on its site and its relationship with the path of the sun, and secondly enabling people to know where they are within a building. This sense of orientation comes from contact with the world outside, which may be gained from an awareness of the daylight pattern even where there is no view out. Orientation should always be considered to ensure that the most advantageous of natural daylighting is adopted at the outset.

The orientation of the window to the sun will significantly affect the amount of solar gain and the consequent degree of penetration of sunlight. For instance, a north-facing window will admit little solar radiation compared with one facing south, west or east. For a south-facing façade, the sun is high in the sky at the hottest part of the day in summer and, consequently, solar penetration can effectively be avoided using shading. For this reason, a preferred orientation for a building will often be with the longer axis aligned east-west, with solar shading on the south face.

Natural daylighting through North windows does not cast shadows on the task; accordingly, it is recommended for illuminating classrooms and other teaching spaces because it is composed mainly of indirect diffuse light coming from the sky. Direct sun on North orientation can be experienced in only very short periods in the early morning or late afternoon during the middle of the summer when schools are closed. The south can be accepted as the best orientation for daylighting due to the relatively higher quantity of light consistent throughout a

day as well as ease of solar control resulting from a high solar altitude angle. Horizontal shading devices are appropriate for this orientation. The second-best orientation for daylighting, although the quantity of light is rather low, is north due to the consistency and color quality of light as well as a relatively less need for solar control. Small fins can be used in this orientation. The worst orientations for daylighting are east and west due to the inconsistency in the amount of light throughout a day and a difficulty of solar control resulting from a low solar altitude angle. Dynamic shading devices or closely arranged eggcrate systems can be used for this orientation which in turn decreases the internal light levels and fails to maintain view, Lechner (13). In terms of solar gains, an optimum orientation for a site would give maximum radiation in the underheated period and minimum radiation in the overheated period. Lechner (13) south is the most advantageous orientation, allowing variations of which up to a certain degree to the southeast and southwest can be tolerable, due to the admittance of the greatest amount of radiation at the winter and the least amount at the summer. Whereas facades facing east and west receive maximum sunlight during summer minimum in winter with admittance of sunlight for only half of each day. Thus, these orientations are the least advantageous.

2.1.3.2 Area, Shape and Location of Windows.

Daylighting, though, is more than lighting tasks: it is also about lighting spaces so that they are pleasant to be in. In general, people prefer spaces to appear bright; 'light and airy' is a common description. To create this effect the window area must provide sufficient light and the windows be placed in positions where they illuminate building surfaces, particularly the walls which form a major element in the normal field of view. Window area not only affects the amount of daylight but also influences heat gain and heat loss. The daylight and thermal

conditions should equally be taken into consideration: that is, the greater the window area the greater the amount of daylight, but also the greater the heat loss and heat gain unless other elements are introduced to counter these effects.

The appropriate window area is related to the required internal illuminance and the typical sky conditions in daylighting design. The greater the window area the greater will be the amount of light received indoors. Baker and Steemers (4) In a side lit space, the area of a window is recommended to be about 30 % to 35 % of the total area of the window wall and is also recommended to be equal to or greater than 1/16 of the floor area. Heerwagen (10) However, reduction in window area reduce glare and some kind of a control should be provided for large windows to reduce the transmission or visible area of bright sky. Hopkinson (6) In terms of window shape, wide horizontal windows provide a relatively uniform illumination distribution across a space when compared to the vertical strip windows. As a result, at same conditions of environmental brightness, a wide horizontal window caused no more glare than the square one; a tall narrow window provided the most glare and the window had a length to height ratio of 10:1 caused the least glare. As a guideline, the width of the window should be greater than the height and the window width should be at least 60 % to 75 % of the total width of the window-wall. Heerwagen (10), For a given area of opening, although the mean daylight factor is only weakly affected by the window locations, the distribution of light will generally improves with the increase in the mounting height of the window in the wall. Therefore, high windows, clerestories or skylights are excellent for daylighting whereas low windows at eye level are for view. Baker and Steemers (4) Moreover, daylight will be more uniformly distributed in a space with spread out windows rather than concentrated ones as well as in a space with windows on more than one wall.

An overhang is the simplest form of the solar control devices, relying upon the solar geometry i.e., it obstructs the part of the sky through which the sun passes. It is used to avoid the high-altitude sun while allowing view thus they are not useful in low altitude sun which is mostly avoided by vertical fins or egg crate systems blocking the view

2.1.3.3 Window Head Height to Room Depth Ratio.

Although, Measurements vary according to an architect's design brief, a general rule of thumb as outlined by AIA, American Institute of Architects (18)— are as follow;

- Maximum room depth is 2 to 2.5 times window head height for continuous fenestration and curtain wall construction where window heads are close to the ceiling
- Room depth is about 1.5 times the window head height for continuous or near continuous windows under overcast skies and 3 to 3.5 times under a clear sky
- 2 times for continuous clear glazed and curtain walling
- 1.5 or 2.5 times with a south facing light shelf

Note that all these rules, and those discussed below, apply to unilateral, or single sided, daylighting unless otherwise specified. It is also a general guide regardless of regional climate. In addition, a number of authors give a variant of this rule with a floor depth of twice the ceiling height, e.g. Yeang, (17)

— Limiting Room Depth;

A general rule of thumb as outlined by (CIBSE), Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers (19)— are as follow;

- (i) Maximum floor depth of approximately 8 meters and ceiling height of 2.7 meters for adequate daylight and ventilation
- (ii) Five meters for window, or rooflight, illuminating a room from one side.
- (iii) 3.6 meters for full and effective daylighting.

Of course, some contextual factors and internal room characteristics could contribute to the significant differences in some of these recommendations given that many are related to the same building type and general location. For example: Average diffuse transmittance, reflectance, the distance etc.

— **Basic consideration for visual Comfort and Performance**

- **Veiling reflections:** Veiling reflections of high brightness light sources off specular, or shiny, surfaces obscure details by reducing contrast. They should be avoided, particularly where critical visual tasks occur.
- **Distribution:** Introduce as much controlled daylight as deep as possible into a building interior. The human eye can adjust to high levels of luminance as long as it is evenly distributed. In general, light which reaches a task indirectly (such as having bounced from a white wall) will provide better lighting quality than light which arrives directly from a natural or artificial source.
- **Glare:** The aim of an efficient daylighting design is not only to provide illuminance levels that are sufficient for good performance, but also to maintain a comfortable and pleasing atmosphere. Glare, or excessive brightness contrast within the field of view, is an aspect of lighting that can cause discomfort to occupants. The human eye can function quite well if extreme levels of brightness are present in the same field of view.

- **Variety:** Some contrast in brightness levels may be desirable in a space for visual effectiveness. Dull uniformity in lighting can lead to tiredness and lack of attention- neither of which is compatible with a productive environment. Often, a good daylighting solution will integrate a "blast" of beam daylight in a circulation area for visual interest and to help lead occupants through a building. The human eye is naturally attracted to this bright area and can be useful in guiding people down an otherwise dull corridor.

2.1.3.4 Shading Strategy

Shading Devices can take several forms; horizontal, vertical and their combination.

There are two classifications of shading devices according to their location;

Exterior Shading Device

That is, a device attached to the building skin or an extension of the skin itself, to keep out unwanted solar heat. Exterior systems are typically more effective than interior systems in blocking solar heat gain. A form of exterior shading device is the use of wooden screening devices which are popular in hot climates. Such screening is a protection against direct solar radiation and reduces the problem of glare. Note: Glare and unwanted solar gains are usually dealt with shading devices which also frequently interfere with the admission of light. In terms of glare, the main issue in window design is to reduce the luminance differences between windows, surrounding surfaces and the ambient conditions of the interior space.

Various forms include:

1. Horizontal overhang

2. Vertical louvers or fins
3. Slope overhang (horizontal & vertical)
4. Egg crate
5. Shade screen.

	Descriptive Name	Best Orientation*	Comments
	Overhang Horizontal panel	South, east, west	Traps hot air Can be loaded by snow and wind
	Overhang Horizontal louvers in horizontal plane	South, east, west	Free air movement Snow or wind load is small Small scale
	Overhang Horizontal louvers in vertical plane	South, east, west	Reduces length of overhang View restricted Also available with miniature louvers
	Overhang Vertical panel	South, east, west	Free air movement No snow load View restricted
	Vertical fin	North	Restricts view if used on east and west orientations
	Vertical fin slanted	East, West	Slant toward north Restricts view significantly
	Eggcrate	East, west	For very hot climates View very restricted Traps hot air
	Eggcrate with slanted fins	East, west	Slant toward north View very restricted Traps hot air For very hot climates

Fig. 4. Exterior shading devices Lechner (13)

— Design consideration for the use of exterior shading devices

- Design the building to shade itself. If shading attachments are not aesthetically acceptable, use the building form itself for exterior shading. Set the window back in a deeper wall section or extend elements of the skin to visually blend with envelope structural features.
- Use a horizontal form for south windows. For example, awnings, overhangs, recessed windows. Also somewhat useful on the east and west. Serves no function on the north.
- Use vertical forms on east and west windows, such as vertical fins or recessed windows. Vertical fins or recessed windows are also useful on the north to block early morning and late afternoon low sun.
- Give west and south windows shading priority. Morning sun is usually not a serious heat gain problem. If your budget is tight, invest in west and south shading only.
- Design shading for glare relief as well. Use exterior shading to reduce glare by partially blocking occupants' view of the too-bright sky. Exterior surfaces also help smooth out interior daylight distribution

Interior Shading Device

Interior shading alone has limited ability to control solar gain. All interior systems are less effective than a good exterior system because they allow the sun's heat to enter the building. They also depend on user behavior, which can't be relied upon.

Various forms include:

- 1) Shades
- 2) Blinds

3) Draperies

— **Design consideration for the use of interior shading devices**

- Interior shading is best used for glare control and backup shading. Supply user-operated devices that occupants can adjust to their individual comfort needs.
- Use devices that still allow daylight in. Blinds and open-weave shades are good choices for filtering but not blocking all light.

— **Difference, Advantages & Disadvantages**

In terms of thermal performance, because the internal shading devices control the sun inside the building, they are not so much useful in rejecting the heat to interior while exterior shading devices release most of the absorbed energy to the outside. However, external devices have also disadvantages such that they have to be weatherproof as well as to resist strong winds, Baker and Steemers (4). In terms of solar control, the direct solar component (excess illumination and heat) is effectively controlled with exterior devices while the diffuse component are usually controlled with additional indoor device or controlled within the glazing. The required shading period of any building, depend on both the climate and occupancy of the building, Lechner (13).

An overhang is the simplest form of the solar control devices, relying upon the solar geometry i.e. it obstructs the part of the sky through which the sun passes. It is used to avoid the high altitude sun while allowing view thus they are not useful in low altitude sun which is mostly avoided by vertical fins or eggcrate systems blocking the view. In terms of daylighting, there must be a strong ground-reflected light to illuminate the underside of the overhang which should have a high reflectance. Horizontal louvers serving the same

purpose have advantages over overhangs such as they reduce structural loads by allowing wind and snow to pass through and by avoiding the gathering of warm air under in summer. Louvers in a vertical or horizontal plane painted a light color are also beneficial because they only block direct sunlight but they reflect diffused sunlight, Lechner (13).

On the other hand, light redirecting shading devices will not only improve the quality of daylighting, but also enhance the illuminance in the darkest part of the room while the use of a sole shading devices such as an overhang in deep spaces or spaces potentially poor for ground-reflected light will worsen the illumination at the back of the room.

Fig. 5 Wu, W. & Ng (20)

2.1.4 FENESTRATION AND DAYLIGHTING IN SCHOOL DESIGN

The quality of daylight in educational premises is connected with several different aspects. First, daylight availability on the working plane should be sufficiently high to allow students and teachers to accomplish easily their visual tasks. The distribution of uniform

daylighting within the classroom is desired; indeed, excessive daylight disuniformity may strain students' visual field.

Moreover, glare problems should be avoided. Glare occurs when a too bright light source falls within the visual field and can cause visual discomfort or even temporary visual impairment. In relation to daylight, glare is mainly related to the view of direct sunlight, which can be avoided by suitable orientation and shading devices.

Daylight is intrinsically good, and has been proven to enhance melatonin suppression. Melatonin is a hormone responsible for the regulation of the body clock, and its presence facilitates sleep; during the day, its concentration in the body is reduced, and daylight plays a very important role in this process. However, the spectral properties of glazing may mainly alter daylight spectral distribution, thus diminishing its circadian efficacy.

2.1.4.1 Daylighting Systems

There are generally three main ways by which daylight is admitted to a room: through the side of the room namely as side lighting, through the ceiling namely, as top lighting, and through another lit area of a building such as atria namely as borrowed lighting. Sidelighting, however, can be divided into view windows and clerestories (Fig 5). Side windows have the advantage of a view to the outside when the sills are beneath eye levels. A general rule of thumb for daylight penetration in a room is about 1.5 times the window head height, as noted earlier, AIA (18); therefore, a separate high-side window can be used to bring the daylight deeper into the room. Clerestory windows (in fig 5) admit light from the brighter part of the sky and therefore, it increases the contrast between inside and outside which could cause glare, DfEE (22). Roof lights (in Fig 5) admit the light from the highest part of the sky which is generally unobstructed. They also need careful consideration in terms of glare from contrast if the glazing

is visible from normal viewing positions. Use exterior or interior shading devices should, then, to obstruct the direct view to the bright sky. However, they provide more even daylight when equipped with shading or diffusing devices. Finally, borrowed light can contribute to the light levels in darker areas of the rooms away from window walls.

2.1.4.2 Basic Principles of Daylighting in Schools

There are specific features of daylight in schools that make it different from other buildings. The reason behind the specificity of daylight in schools is the educational nature of the building, which requires appropriate illumination for reading and writing, as well as providing a healthy, stimulating and inspiring space for children to learn. “One of the first principles of daylighting in schools is to avoid glare in teaching spaces” DfEE (22). Almost all complaints of glare from windows are attributable to direct sunlight. In domestic-scale situations, where occupants are free to move around and to draw the curtains, solar glare is of little consequence. Where occupants are confined to a desk, drawing board or computer screen, direct sunlight can be a major source of glare. It also causes overheating. Often effective remedies for solar heat gain, such as external shading, also protect occupants against visual discomfort; therefore, one should design shading device mindfully. This requires preventing direct sunlight penetration and avoiding other sources of glare such as a glaring view such as the bright sky or a contrastive window wall colour. Instead, a uniform and gentle daylight is preferred for teaching and task based spaces. The location of daylight apertures has significant impact on causing glare as well as distribution of light throughout the classroom. When daylight apertures are located in the ceiling, the likelihood of glare is reduced as long as the glazing cannot be seen directly from normal viewing positions. Besides, the evenness of distribution of light is increased. It is more

difficult to achieve uniform illuminance with windows, as there is more quantity of light next to them, CHPS (24).

— **Reasons & Practical Solutions of Daylighting Principle**

- Preventing Direct Sunlight Penetration to avoid visual & thermal discomfort Except in most non-academic based areas. The best daylighting designs are initiated early in the design process of new buildings. The first step in good daylighting design is the thoughtful orientation of the buildings on the site and orientation of the fenestration openings. A carefully oriented building design will allow maximum daylight while minimizing unwanted solar gains. CHPS (24), It is easiest to provide excellent daylight conditions using north-facing windows, since the sun only strikes a north-facing window in early morning and late evening during midsummer. South-facing windows are the next best option because the high angle of the south sun can be easily shaded with a horizontal overhang. East- and west-facing windows are more problematic because when the sun is low in the sky, overhangs or other fixed shading devices are of limited utility. Any window orientation more than 15° off true north or south requires careful assessment to avoid unwanted sun penetration. CHPS (24)
- Provide Gentle, Uniform Illumination to balance and diffuse daylight across the space. Use walls & ceiling as reflective surfaces, light-coloured surfaces to help reflection, daylighting systems such as light shelves/shades. CHPS (24), It is easiest to achieve uniform daylight illumination from top lighting (Clerestory) strategies that distribute light evenly across a large area. The next best approach is to provide daylight from two sides of a space with a combination of view windows and high windows

- Avoid excessive high contrast, which causes glare. Obscure bright views by blinds, louvers, etc. Placing daylight apertures next to reflective surfaces reduces glare in addition to distributing the daylight more evenly. It brightens interior surfaces to reduce their contrast with the bright glazing surface, CHPS (24). Glare can also occur when daylight strikes a reflective surface, like a computer screen or a whiteboard, and produces shiny reflections that make it difficult or impossible to see. It can easily be avoided by reorientation.
- Provide Control of Daylight. For example, use blinds and shades inside or outside. Provide teacher access to blinds or shade controls
- Plan the Layout of Interior Spaces and Locate work areas where appropriate daylight exists from sides or above. Since daylighting illuminance can vary considerably within the space, especially with side lighting, it is important to locate work areas where appropriate daylighting exists. Perhaps more importantly, visual tasks (especially the teaching wall) should be located to reduce the probability of discomfort or disabling glare, CHPS (24).

— Daylighting Systems Consideration

To select a system, the designer must understand:

1. The function of the window or other opening(s),
2. The function of the system, and
3. The interplay of the system with other systems

Based on CHPS (24) design consideration;

- View Windows: The most accessible view, applicable in all climate regions

- Clerestory view: To increase daylighting, mostly useful for academic space and for a better ambient. Also Applicable to all climate regions

- Clerestory With light Shelf: To improve daylight distribution and to keep the contrast and glare low. Applicable to most school spaces (academic and non-academic) and all climate region

- Central Top lighting (saw tooth roof design): suitable for even daylight distribution and for avoiding glare problems. Applicable in single story or top floor classrooms, libraries, multipurpose spaces and all climate region

- Extra Daylighting: To illuminate the deep end of classrooms remote from window walls or any other space that happens to lack enough windows. Applicable in spaces close to corridor-lit atrium and all climate region. This extra daylight redirecting systems can contribute to the distribution of daylight to other spaces in the core of a building; daylight-redirecting systems should be applied simultaneously to control glare. Windows facing an atrium have less daylight potential than windows facing an open courtyard. Even if borrowed light from interior windows does not significantly increase daylight levels to an interior space, the presence of these windows may improve light distribution and make a visual link between a space located in the core of a building and other zones of the building.

— **General School Design Recommendation:**

- Building is oriented such that maximum light will be allowed in from the north and south faces, which is easier to control, rather than from the east and west faces, which results in excessive heat gain, as noted earlier. Plympton & Conway (30)

- To optimize daylighting, clerestory windows are used on the south-facing classrooms. The clerestory windows are made of a polycarbonate material that provides a translucent surface for the sunlight to pass through, yet is lighter than glass and less susceptible to breakage, Herbert M. Eckerlin (25). A sloping metal roof will improve daylighting by bouncing light into the clerestories.
- The north-facing classrooms have tall windows to let daylight penetrate deep into the space.
- Currently in conceptual design, the sloping metal roof will also be used for rainwater collection for the cooling tower; water is typically purchased from the city— representing significant cost savings. Plympton & Conway (30)
- Increase perimeter daylight zones-extend the perimeter footprint to maximize the usable daylighting area.
- Allow daylight penetration high in a space. Windows located high in a wall or in roof; monitors and clerestories will result in deeper light penetration and reduce the likelihood of excessive brightness.
- Reflect daylight within a space to increase room brightness. A light shelf, if properly designed, has the potential to increase room brightness and decrease window brightness.
- Slope ceilings to direct more light into a space. Sloping the ceiling away from the fenestration area will help increase the surface brightness of the ceiling further into a space.
- Avoid direct beam daylight on critical visual tasks. Poor visibility and discomfort will result if excessive brightness differences occur near critical visual tasks.

- Filter daylight. The harshness of direct light can be filtered with vegetation, curtains, louvers, or the like, and will help distribute light.
- Understand that different building orientations will benefit from different daylighting strategies; for example, light shelves-which are effective on south facades-are often ineffective on east or west elevations of buildings.

2.1.4.3 Classrooms Layout Design Considerations

Main problems for designing a day-lit classroom.

- 1) What is a suitable and practical method of measuring and predicting daylighting in the classroom?
- 2) What is the minimum natural illumination required in a classroom for general teaching purposes?
- 3) Is it desirable to recommend the minimum reflectance of the walls and ceilings in a classroom?

Fig. 6 Three-Zone Layout, Michael and Gary (23)

— Two basic classroom layout classification based on their illumination area:

Since most school buildings have a three-zone (classroom - corridor - classroom) layout (fig 6), with the classrooms aligned along the two sides of the communication space (the corridor), this means that classrooms that have vertical windows are illuminated from one side only. An alternative to this concept, which can provide better daylighting, is a two-zone (classroom - corridor) form of school building. This provides the possibility of illuminating the classrooms from two sides by using the additional light that comes from the corridor.

- Classrooms with one-sided illumination - the three-zone form
- Classrooms with two-sided illumination - the two-zone form

Despite the problems for designing a day lit classroom, as cited earlier, there are general rule of thumb for orientation design consideration; “One-sided illumination of classrooms does not meet the average and minimum daylight factor criteria even in the case of minimum classroom depth (7.2 m) and maximum classroom height (3.8 m). Required daylighting conditions can be met only by additional roof light openings, which do not allow multi-storey building form. Therefore the most effective design from visual comfort point of view is two-zone form of school building with two-sided illumination of the classrooms. All analyzed classrooms shapes in such buildings provide basic requirements, minimum and average daylight factor, as well as good daylight uniformity. Buildings with narrow corridor are the best solution”. Bezjak (21)

— Corridor Design

Apart from the two-zone form of school building which enables the classrooms illumination from two-sides. In addition to the mentioned overhead window, another very

important factor in the illumination process is the corridor width. This influences the quantity of additional daylight entering the classroom through the overhead indoor window. Two different corridor widths are advised, Bezjak (21): -

- 2.40 m, as a minimum, empty corridor width
- 3.60 m, as a more comfortable corridor (or hallway) width that would enable it to be used as a communication space, or for educational and social purposes.

— Desk Orientation

The location of the student desk inside the classroom has a great impact on the visual comfort of the student. Each student position has a different field of view, which is a function of the viewer point and the center of interest (on the task). Measurement criteria such as Contrasting luminance in the field of view should be used to aid and improve visual performance and comfort. It is desirable to make the visual task the brightest object in the field of view. According to Baker, Fanchiott (9), the following luminance ratios within the field of view should be aimed at: between task and darker surrounding 3:1; between task and remote darker surfaces 10:1; between light sources and surroundings 20:1; maximum contrast 40:1; and highlight object for emphasis 50:1. Also, luminance levels as a function of position in the field of vision should be within acceptable levels, as defined by Baker, Fanchiott (9). These values are used in this study as benchmarks to investigate visual comfort problems caused by classroom design.

2.1.4.4 Classroom Comfort and Glazing Considerations

A good layout first involves a careful consideration of the climate in which the classroom is located; to increment daylight levels in classrooms without introducing glare issues. First step, geometrical layout and orientation. First, different layout plans, namely the one-sided open corridor, the one-sided closed corridor and the double-sided corridor. Then, parametric variations for the orientation, the geometrical features such as depth of classrooms and corridors, and the façade characteristics (amount and type of glazing and shading types). The aim is to maximize the number of summer thermal comfort hours while minimizing the heating and lighting energy demand. The main outcomes reveal how the best results pertain to the double-sided corridor configuration, mainly south-oriented, in order to take advantage of the solar gains during winter. Different glazing solutions, such as single clear panes, as well as different external shading devices such as an opaque fixed overhang and a horizontal louver system, are modeled in the way Zhang, Bokel (29) describes, Zhang.

Factors mostly influencing comfort conditions in a classroom are, in order:

- Window to wall ratio
- Solar heat gain coefficient (SHGC) of the glazing
- Shading devices
- Orientation
- The windows' U-value

In particular, low U-values are favorably judged for high window to wall ratio (WWR) configurations in order to reduce the outgoing heat flux, while overhangs and louvers are mainly seen as corrective systems to over-sized openings. Indeed, by means of both objective

and subjective observations, it emerged that in their actual configurations (i.e., no external shading devices in place but only internal curtains) the rooms are often sufficiently daylit but daylight is not evenly distributed. This led to the curtains being pulled down to avoid direct sunlight on desks or on the blackboard, thus requiring artificial lights to be turned on even on sunny days. The design of proper external shadings is thus required in such cases.

The influence of the surrounding environment (Shadows cast by the surrounding buildings) must be carefully considered when defining the classrooms' layout and shape, in order to not severely penalize students' visual comfort. Wu, W. & Ng (20)

— **External Shading Devices for Classrooms**

For classrooms oriented towards the east-west, the use of overhangs is typical to reduce or completely block direct sunlight during the summer season.

- Design of an external overhang by means of shading angles
- Geometrical parameters parametrically varied for the design of a solar screen device

This device design is able to block direct sunlight while allowing the indirect light component to be diffused into the space thanks to multiple reflections from the external blades to the interior ceiling. The Architect should investigate louver numbers, screen depth ratio, screen tilt angle and WWR, as well as their interaction with the solar reflectance value of the screen materials for better visual and thermal comfort result.

South-facing classrooms, if well shaded by external overhangs, do not usually show so high brightness levels to represent potential glare issues. On the other hand, north-oriented classrooms are the best performing in terms of both quantity of light (mainly diffuse from the sky) and avoidance of glare, as light penetrates indirectly into the classroom.

2.1.5 DAYLIT SCHOOLS AND ENERGY PERFORMANCE

Natural daylighting not only provides better learning environments but also provides schools with dramatic energy savings. Therefore, by using daylighting as the main source of illumination in schools in combination with manual lighting controls, schools can reduce or eliminate electric lights during daylight or schooling hours. Under sunny conditions, some systems can increase daylight penetration, reduce cooling loads, and make the variation uniform between the brighter area near the window and the darker interior zone. Cost and energy savings result from the more efficient use of light without added solar heat gains and cooling loads. For cloudy conditions, louver and blind systems can be energy-efficient if operated properly because most systems will provide less interior light than would be admitted by clear, unobstructed glazing Rubin A.I., (27). With reflective louver systems (e.g., those placed in the upper portion of a window to avoid reflected glare), illuminance levels can be increased under cloudy and sunny conditions when the sun is near-normal to the window, Inoue (28).

2.1.6 CASE STUDY 1

NAME: ALBERT EINSTEIN HIGH SCHOOL

LOCATION: Bagnols-Sur-Cèze, France

ARCHITECT: N+B Architectes

YEAR: 2010

Text description provided by the architects: The Albert Einstein High School, BAGNOLS-SUR-CÈZE, FRANCE, Brassens site, is a big building of the 60's. Built with a model, it is composed by high linear buildings from 60 to 80 cm length. Realize low heights buildings, low influence on the ground to get a better distribution and space's occupation. This flexibility allows adapting itself to the program and to the discipline in constant evolution. The project draws one's inspiration from campus model which presents the advantage to be flexible and to allow a better identification. This intervention process also allows to students to find easily a way and fit into a social life while being supervised (easy reading of circulations, gratitude of spaces). To think of a sustainable development crosses well on by the qualitative consideration of materials, a technical work on the management of the energies, but also by a logic the layout of places.

Analysis: The intervention that are propose allows restoring coherence and featuring to the set by means of a new spatial scenography. Its localization offers direct connection with the cafeteria, restaurant place, administration, workshop, general teaching room, school life. Here gather the students during their free time. That is why it is necessary to propose qualities of specific spaces, easily appropriable, playful and to bring a feature to the exteriors arrangements.

Fig. 7's showing circulation, façade and fenestration design

Fig. 8 Ground floor: ACADEMIC BLOCK

Fig. 9 Sections

2.1.7 CASE STUDY 2

NAME: BAILLY SCHOOL COMPLEX

LOCATION: Saint-Denis, France

ARCHITECT: MIKOU STUDIO

YEAR: 2010

Text description provided by the architects: [The school complex of Bailly is situated in Saint-Denis, France, on a changing territory. The expression of the project is inspired by this specific

context of the material used – glazed brick – and by the idea of the roof, which give reference to the lanterns of the cathedrals. Its base of brick functions as an interspace area to access both schools, the recreation centre and at the same time serve like the connection area for the various functions.]

Analysis: The classrooms are organised in the north-south transverse on two levels, which end on the firewall, with a glazed screen-printed façade to protect the intimacy of the children. Placed on the north and south end of the site, they are protected by noise and acoustic screen made up of circular tubes of different densities from the west which also absorb the noise during the recreation, they are structured by horizontal circulations. Each schoolyard is extended visually one level higher by the garden, accessible by a ramp connected from the schoolyard. These gardens, important for the classrooms on the higher levels, bring freshness to the project and enable the children to get fresh air between the lessons and to connect with the schoolyard while walking on the protected and planted way.

Fig. 10's showing glazed screen-printed façade and fenestration design with use of the roof

Fig. 11 Ground Floor

Fig. 12 First Floor

Fig. 13 Sections

Fig. 14 Fenestration design detail with the use of saw-tooth roofs

2.1.8 CASE STUDY 3

NAME: MANSUETO HIGH SCHOOL

LOCATION: Chicago, USA

ARCHITECT: WHEELER KEARNS ARCHITECTS

YEAR: 2017

Text description provided by the architects: The design of 67,000-sq-ft Mansueto High School, supports the goal of organization around a central green space that emulates a college quadrangle and allows high schoolers to envision a college future.

Analysis: The two-story structure, with a dark brick exterior and a light, gray metal panel interior, wraps almost completely around a landscaped courtyard. The use of masonry anchors the building's identity, providing a sense of protection, and shielding interior functions from the traffic noise created along the busy industrial thoroughfare. **Fig. 15** shows facade

Fig. 16 Site Plan & Layout

- First Floor
- 1 Entry Plaza
 - 2 Corridor
 - 3 Office
 - 4 Classroom
 - 5 Laboratory
 - 6 Kitchen
 - 7 Gymnasium

- Second Floor
- 1 Entry Plaza
 - 2 Corridor
 - 3 Office
 - 4 Classroom
 - 5 Laboratory

Fig. 17 Plans

Fig. 18 Fenestration

Features

2.1.9 CASE STUDY 4

NAME: Lycee Schorge Secondary School

LOCATION: Koudougou, Burkina Faso

ARCHITECT: Kéré Architecture

YEAR: 2016

Text description provided by the architects. Located in the third most populated city in Burkina Faso, the Lycée Schorge Secondary School will not only set a new standard for educational excellence in the region, it will also provide a source of inspiration by showcasing locally-sourced building materials in an innovative and modern way.

Analysis: A vernacular design, The walls of the building are made from locally-harvested laterite stone, which, when first extracted from the earth, can be easily cut and shaped into bricks. The material functions really well as a wall system for the classrooms because of its thermal mass capabilities, which aid its thermal comfort. Natural ventilation and illuminated the interiors is another goal of this design. The wave-like pattern of plaster and concrete components are slightly offset from each other, allowing the interior space to breathe and expel hot stagnant air.

Fig. 19 Plan

Fig. 20 Axonometric view

Fig. 21 Elevation and Section

Fig. 22 Axonometric view

Fig. 23 3D

Chapter 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This Chapter presents the methodological procedures adopted in the study. It covers the study population, sample frame/technique, research design and data sources. It also covers method employed in the selection of the study zones. The chapter deals with methods to evaluate proper daylighting and fenestration design. As suggested by CHPS (24) one general category of tools and methods for evaluating daylighting and fenestration is physical models.

3.2 APPROACH OF THE STUDY

The research has been conceived to improve the visual comfort and thermal quality of a typical secondary school for the schooling population of the Ilaje community, and the impact of several design consideration on student performance. One of the possible approaches to achieving a good daylighting system in schools is diagnosing the typical daylighting challenges in secondary schools, such as glare, cross ventilation.

3.3 METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research is the process of inquiry that seeks to understand the nature of its subjects; it is concerned with assessment of attitudes, opinions and behavior. The information is gathered using variables measured on nominal or ordinal scales; that are also called as qualitative data; and if the analysis is done to establish the variation in the situation, phenomenon or problem without qualifying it Walliman (31).

Quantitative research on the other hand, the study is classified as quantitative if you want to quantify the variation in a phenomena, situation, problem or issue; if information is gathered using predominantly quantitative variables; and if the analysis is geared to ascertain magnitude of the variation. Walliman (31).

The research usually involves observations, description of the Scio-economic conditions of the Ilaje community, and a number of participants with in-depth interviews. By using literature review, this limitation are addressed. Literature review is a critical review, summary, interpretation or evaluation of existing literature to determine current knowledge of a topic. By this means, personal interviews will be supplemented with information gathered by other researches on the subject in order to deduce results. Materials will also include case studies. The analysis technique employed in the location survey and analysis is that the qualitative research method. the necessities for this research analysis concerned getting correct data on the study area.

3.4.1 DATA COLLECTION

Various research procedures were employed. Some of these were:

- Observation (participant and holistic).
- Field study (available statistical data).
- Interviews and questionnaires. Information on social services, public facilities, travel distance from public facilities and other amenities, average number of student in a household, and security, etc., was collected through a questionnaire developed by neighborhood residents and occupants. This included personal presence on and around the site to document elements of the

community's social lives; their beliefs, taste, interests, cultural symbolic symbols, spatial use such as their courtyard spaces, and suitable architectural and building technology, etc.

3.4.2 PRIMARY DATA

The primary data for this study are obtained directly from the field, that is, first hand data through direct observation, feedback obtained from personal interviews with teenagers, concerned persons, parents and local government officials. Primary data were collected through photography and personal observation. This qualitative research type evidently requires a lot of information in order to justify its essence. Moreover, a research in the field of an impactful recreational planning needs copious primary data to make for research reliability. In this study, there were interviews with residents located in the core neighborhoods along Ilaje Road, the relevant authorities and teenagers/students who constitute the bulk of the respondents. The “one on one” interview method employed. The data derived through interviews was mainly from persons aged 15 years and above. This was exclusively designed to capture the right persons who are involved in the academic sphere from different age groups. In order to get the best of the physical attributes of the urban area (Ilaje), I, along with a research group made series of field trips on monthly interval between May, 2021 and September, 2021 (Although, hampered by the COVID-19 lock down we were able to meet our goal). This helped in updating information and in the photographic capturing of the existing schools and other educational facilities.

3.4.3 SECONDARY DATA

The secondary data were drawn from published works of other researchers in journals, textbooks, monographs and official records from local government, educational commission;

both aerial and other maps (either in their natural form, in modified, or updated format) were channeled towards the goal of the study. The reliability of these data was verified, to various degree, before they were utilized in the study. This method of thorough examination helped in nearly all the maps and graphical illustrations used in this work. In like manner, the up-to-date information that could be generated from physical structures or elements was ultimately made possible with the use of photographs (a veritable instrument in primary information generation). This form of harmonious relationship that was made possible helped to filter out unwanted information.

3.4.4 RELEVANT SOURCES

Due to COVID-19 lockdown interaction with relevant Government authorities and agencies such as Universal Basic Education Commission of Nigeria (UBE), were only done online to obtain relevant information. Local government authorities to obtain information, to obtain the original site plan and other existing educational facilities all to aid the eventual design and make it more sustainable.

— **Literature Reviews:** This consists of published works, relevant journals, articles, newspapers, magazine prints, reviews, and various projects done in the past on related topics. These are all secondary source of data since the information obtained is not firsthand Interviews. To ascertain certain information, oral interviews had to be conducted in the study area and with professionals of the subject under consideration. This helped to authenticate information and data obtained, thus reducing errors, inadequacies, and inaccuracies. Library Research Involves sourcing information from libraries online and accessing physical libraries and archives such as the University of Lagos, Department of Architecture Library. The major source of data collected was both:

- National Population Commission: to determine the current population and population growth of the area.
- Google Earth: to source for current satellite images of the subject area

My research group's delegates received a warm response from most residents, while others refused to give information on some sensitive issues such as employment status and income. In addition, many local residents claimed we were spreading COVID-19 even though the government had already lifted the lock down restrictions and we were taking all necessary government issued percussion, while others were afraid that we were whistleblowers working for the state government.

3.5.1 DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS.

There were several data collection instruments that aids in the data gathering process. These included observation guides, use of photographic materials and interview. The instruments were effective and useful in the collection of data needed for the study Interview method.

3.5.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is the framework of research methods and techniques chosen by a researcher. The design of a research topic explains the type of research (experimental, survey, correlational, semi-experimental, review) and also its sub-type (experimental design, research problem, descriptive case-study). A design researcher's job is to learn about people in a specific context to identify the areas in which a designed solution can have better impact. In the words of César Astudillo: "It's research that helps me understand the points or articulation of reality in which I can apply my design potential, I don't want to understand how much the world weights, I want to learn which one is the lever that I have to push to move it".

From this forgoing, therefore, this study has adopted a fixed type of design. The daylight conditions were simulated in the rooms presented in the figures, and both the quantitative analysis (the survey) of the students' opinions and the qualitative one (the interview) were performed among the population from two schools as a case study (CMS grammar school & St Finbarrs College, 535 meters away). Principally, the research design employed these two related steps to achieving the study's aim: First, Interview surveys with flexible approach, are conducted along a standardized format with both official stakeholders and average student alike. Second, personal observation and Photography; are employed to monitor daylighting impact through frequent visits.

The fieldwork consisted of the initial visits to the examine area, surveys, and interviews. Reconnaissance Survey The look at started with the first reconnaissance survey at 10th of May 2021, followed by three other visit, all in an effort to try to familiarize with the study area. Direct commentary helped in the investigation. The normal month-to-month visits additionally enabled the researcher to be able to access large varied number of students in which questionnaires were given. Although, this monthly visit was halted by the COVID-19 lockdown. Field Work, Interviews timing, and particular days were into consideration in the management of the questionnaires. Most of the questionnaires were administered in the afternoon during weekdays; the period in question is just after school closing hours.

— **Treatment of Research Questions and Objectives**

For a good understanding of the method of data analysis used in this work, the under listed summary report provides information on the core objectives of this work.

- To highlight student awareness on natural daylighting

- To highlight student perception on daylighting
- To determine the nature of demand for better daylighting system in schools
- Examine various negative factors due to excess or insufficient natural daylighting

Questionnaire and Interview Methods

3.5.2.1 Questionnaire

The questionnaire and additional interviews were carried out with the students inhabiting differently oriented classrooms. The survey was done among the students of various ages and gender and of diverse education profiles and faculties. There were 65% of male and 35% of female examinees. The questionnaire was distributed in the month of May to 60 students, and in July 2021, when this number was 50. The questions asked in the survey were as follows— question 1: “Do you consider that daylighting is important for your work performance as a student?” The answer scale ranged from “very great importance” to “very low importance”. The question 2: “How do you rate your satisfaction with the amount of natural light in your classroom?”, and the answer scale ranged from “very great satisfaction” to “very low satisfaction”. The question 3: “How do you rate your visual comfort?” The question 4 related to the excess daylight: “Daylighting problems like glare regularly affect your performance as a student.”

The Arithmetic mean and standard deviation was used to establish the extent to which students perceived daylight illumination as a determinant for effective students’ task performance in classroom. On a 5-point scale, the decision rules assigned to the students’ responses thus: Very great extent/importance/satisfaction, (4.50-5.000); Great

extent/importance/satisfaction, (3.50-4.49); Moderate extent/importance/satisfaction, (2.50-3.49); Low extent/importance/satisfaction, (1.50-2.49); and Very low extent/importance/satisfaction, (1.00-1.49). The null hypothesis was tested with Z-test of independent group means at 0.05 level of significance for two tailed to establish whether there was no significant difference in the responses among students from CMS grammar school & St Finbarrs College respectively on the extent to which they perceived daylight illumination as a determinant for effective work performance as a student

3.5.2.2 Interview Method

Within the qualitative interview method, in order to examine the survey results in detail, 30 students were interviewed. The questions asked in the 15-minute interviews comprised the following issues: How often does the student observe daylighting problems like glare, i.e. in which part of the day, and what their opinions on the daylighting conditions in their classrooms were in different parts of the year? The students were asked to express satisfaction with daylight in three parts of the year: cooler dry season, rainy season, and summer season. How important is natural daylighting for your visual comfort? The questions referred to the quantity of lighting in their classrooms, the time of its occurrence, and how they relate the quality of lighting to visual comfort (see **Fig.19** for the interview sheet used)

3.6 DATA ANALYSIS

The results of research Question on the extent to which students from the two secondary schools at CMS grammar school & St Finbarrs College, respectively perceived the impact of daylight illumination as a determinant for effective students' performance presented in. Table 1 used daylight illumination determinant indicators as visual distress (low visual acuity), visual fatigue (straining of eyes), mental fatigue (restlessness), and low visual impression.

Table 1. Students' perception scores on daylight illumination effect on students' performance in classrooms.

Indicator	CMS grammar school		St Finbarrs College		Decision
	X_{cms}	SD_{cms}	X_F	SD_F	
1. Do you consider that daylighting is important for your work performance as a student	3.56	1.08	3.62	1.12	Great Importance
2. How do you rate your satisfaction with the amount of natural light in your classroom?	3.98	1.11	3.88	1.01	Great Satisfaction
3. How do you rate your visual comfort?	3.48	1.03	3.20	0.98	Moderate extent
4. Daylighting problems like glare regularly affect your performance as a student.	3.25	1.00	3.14	0.95	Moderate extent
5. Daylight illumination, which reduces visual distress (low visual acuity), is a determinant for smooth visual work environment.	4.03	1.15	4.07	1.13	Great extent
6. Daylight illumination, which reduces visual fatigue (straining of eyes), is a determinant for accuracy of colour judgment, quality and uniformity in task	3.88	1.13	4.14	0.85	Great extent
7. Daylight illumination, which reduces mental fatigue (restlessness), is a determinant for quantity and uniformity of task.	3.76	0.99	3.88	1.01	Great extent
Grand mean (X_G)	3.71	0.27	3.70	0.37	Great extent

The students' Grand Perception Mean (X_G) scores of 3.71 and 3.70 for CMS grammar school and St Finbarrs College respectively revealed that daylight illumination was a determinant for students' effective performance in classrooms to a great extent. The Grand Mean Standard

Deviations (X_G) of 0.27 to 0.37 for the students' perception response scores from CMS grammar school and St Finbarrs College were Low indicating that the SD means data are clustered around the mean, not widely dispersed with small variability and therefore homogeneous.

— **The Interview Results of Examination of Subjective Student Attitudes**

In the survey, daylighting problem like glare were regularly observed for students in a classroom by a large number of examinees (40% in the Cool dry season and 70% of the examinees in the summer). The answer moderately often was given by 40% in the Cool dry survey and 30% in the summer survey. The percentage of the students who seldom, answered less often was less than 25% of all students (see Fig. 20 for these and results that follow). The Students were largely satisfied with the natural light in classrooms. Most of the examinees (45% in the Cool dry survey and 71% in the summer survey) were satisfied, while there were 7-13% of those who were either dissatisfied or indifferent. In the Cool dry survey, 28% of the examinees were very satisfied, whereas this percentage was lower in the summer survey, 13%. Only 7% of the examinees were very dissatisfied by the amount of illuminance in the Cool dry season, while in the summer survey, the percentage was negligible

INTERVIEW SURVEY SHEET		UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS Department Of Architecture	
Interview on the impact of daylighting in student in relation to different season. All responses are collected anonymously and the information collected is treated with complete confidentiality			
Name:		Sex: M/F	
Date:	School Year:	No. of student in class	
Section A: Daily observation on daylighting conditions			
a) During what period in the day do you observe day light problems the most (morning, midday, afternoon, evening, night)	morning	midday	afternoon
	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
b) What is your opinion on the Daylighting conditions in these periods of the day in your room (1-excellent, 2-great, 3-Good, 4-Bad, 5-Incovenient)	8:00 to 10:00	10:00 to 13:00	13:00 to 15:00
	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Section B: Annual analysis and satisfaction with daylighting			
1. How would you describe daylighting condions at this me of the year? (cool dry season /summer/rainy season)		3. How often do you observe daylighting problems ? (cool dry season /summer/rainy season)	
Much too bright	<input type="text"/>	Very Often	<input type="text"/>
Comfortably bright	<input type="text"/>	Moderately Often	<input type="text"/>
Comfortably neither bright not dark	<input type="text"/>	Seldom	<input type="text"/>
Comfortably dark	<input type="text"/>	Less Often	<input type="text"/>
Much too dark	<input type="text"/>	Never	<input type="text"/>
1a. I would prefer it to be:		4. of what importance is visual comfort to you	
Much brighter	<input type="text"/>	Very great importance	<input type="text"/>
A bit brighter	<input type="text"/>	Great importance	<input type="text"/>
No change	<input type="text"/>	moderate importance	<input type="text"/>
A bit darker	<input type="text"/>	Low importance	<input type="text"/>
Much darker	<input type="text"/>	Very Low importance	<input type="text"/>
2. How would you grade your room on the annual level regarding daylight and comfort for performance effiience? (cool dry season /summer/rainy season)		5. Grade your satisfaction by the amount of daylight in your classroom.	
Very bad	<input type="text"/>	Very great satisfaction	<input type="text"/>
Bad	<input type="text"/>	Great satisfaction	<input type="text"/>
Neither bad nor good	<input type="text"/>	moderate satisfaction	<input type="text"/>
Good	<input type="text"/>	Low satisfaction	<input type="text"/>
Excellent	<input type="text"/>	Very Low satisfaction	<input type="text"/>

Fig. 24 Interview Survey Sheet

Interview result

Fig. 25 Answers to the questions: How often does the student observe daylighting problems

Interview Result

Fig. 26 Answers to the questions: Of what importance is visual comfort to you

Fig. 27 Answers to the questions: Grade your satisfaction by the amount of daylight in your classroom.

Chapter 4: ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

4.1.1 LOCATION, PHYSICAL & REGIONAL SETTING

Ilaje- bariga is a slum settlement within the Bariga community of Shomolu local government area in Lagos metropolis. Ilaje-Bariga is characterized by unplanned developments and squatter settlements, non-conformity with the regional master plan of the metropolis, filthy environment and environmental pollution, traffic, and human congestion as well as lacking basic and fundamental infrastructural amenities. The area of Ilaje-Bariga is about **22 hectares** of land with a perimeter of about **3 kilometers**. Physical structures have been built on **about 91% of the total area**, with open spaces and marshy spots accounting for the remaining 9% of the land area of Ilaje-Bariga home to an estimated population of **20,000 inhabitants**.

Overall, the first impression of Ilaje is of a forsaken neighbourhood. Ilaje fits the Western world's image of a Third World poverty-stricken community. Rich in squalor, densely populated, characterized by hovels and all sorts of substandard housings, dirt-poor economy, an absence of potable water—in all ramifications, the enclave is grossly representative of the sordid underbelly of an overpopulated Lagos with a glaring infrastructural deficit.

In the slum of Ilaje, a class distinction prevails as the community is divided into upper and lower classes. While the upper class is dominantly the indigenes, the lower class is categorized by outsiders.

Although, they live close to the lagoon and the ocean hardly translate into any advantages. Apart from being a source of fish, the body of water around them has been a plague. It breeds diseases.

Fig. 28 showing map of Ilaje- bariga area (Source; Google Maps 2021)

4.1.2 CLIMATIC CHARACTERISTICS, SOIL AND VEGETATION.

This urban area has a tropical climate. Most months of the year are marked by significant rainfall. The short dry season has little impact. This location is classified as Am by Köppen and Geiger. The temperature here averages 26.4 °C | 79.5 °F. The annual rainfall is 1783 mm | 70.2 inch.

Location: Ilaje Rd, Lagos, Shomolu, Lagos
Time: 15.May.2021, 14:26 UTC+1

Solar data for the Location		Geo data for the Location	
Dawn:	06:08:10	Height:	6m
Sunrise:	06:29:58	Latitude:	N 6°31'55.3" 6.53203°
Sun peak level:	12:42:47	Longitude:	E 3°23'38.25" 3.39396°
Sunset:	18:55:39	Timezone:	Africa/Lagos WAT
Dusk:	19:17:29		
Duration:	12h25m41s		
Altitude:	61.98°		
Azimuth:	298.84°		
Shadow length:	3.19	at an object level:	6m

Fig. 29 Solar data on first site visit

Location: Ilaje Rd, Lagos, Shomolu, Lagos
Time: 11.Jul.2021, 14:26 UTC+1

Solar data for the Location		Geo data for the Location	
Dawn:	06:15:08	Height:	6m
Sunrise:	06:37:25	Latitude:	N 6°31'55.3" 6.53203°
Sun peak level:	12:51:59	Longitude:	E 3°23'38.25" 3.39396°
Sunset:	19:06:31	Timezone:	Africa/Lagos WAT
Dusk:	19:28:47		
Duration:	12h29m6s		
Altitude:	62.54°		
Azimuth:	306.74°		
Shadow length:	3.12	at an object level:	6m

Fig. 30 Solar data on another site visit

NB: Most Solar data produced by SunCalc app

Two types of soil structure exist in these environments which are

- Hydromorphic alluvium and,
- Fluvio – marine alluvium

The study area comprises of several levels of topographical grades ranging from ground height below 2.5m to ground height above 10m. The drainage flow in the area depicts movement from high table lands towards low grounds leading to the existence of canals on and off the subject area. It consists of coastal swamp and lowland forest vegetation.

NB: Climate data produced by Meteoblue and en.climate-data.org

— Other Climate Data

Fig. 31 Showing Average Temperatures and Precipitation; The "mean daily maximum" (solid red line) shows the maximum temperature of an average day for every month for Ilaje. Likewise, "mean daily minimum" (solid blue

line) shows the average minimum temperature. The temperatures are highest on average in March, at around 27.9 °C | 82.2 °F. The lowest average temperatures in the year occur in August, when it is around 24.6 °C | 76.3 °F

Fig. 32 Showing Cloudy, Sunny and Precipitation Days. The graph shows the monthly number of sunny, partly cloudy, overcast and precipitation days. Days with less than 20% cloud cover are considered as sunny, with 20-80% cloud cover as partly cloudy and with more than 80% as overcast.

WEATHER BY MONTH // WEATHER AVERAGES SOMOLU

	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Avg. Temperature °C (°F)	27.1 °C (80.8) °F	27.7 °C (81.9) °F	27.9 °C (82.2) °F	27.6 °C (81.6) °F	26.8 °C (80.3) °F	25.6 °C (78) °F	24.8 °C (76.7) °F	24.6 °C (76.3) °F	25 °C (77) °F	25.8 °C (78.4) °F	26.8 °C (80.2) °F	27.1 °C (80.8) °F
Min. Temperature °C (°F)	24.1 °C (75.4) °F	25.3 °C (77.5) °F	25.9 °C (78.7) °F	25.7 °C (78.3) °F	25 °C (77) °F	23.9 °C (75.1) °F	23.3 °C (74) °F	23.1 °C (73.6) °F	23.4 °C (74.1) °F	23.9 °C (75) °F	24.6 °C (76.3) °F	24.4 °C (75.9) °F
Max. Temperature °C (°F)	31.6 °C (88.9) °F	31.7 °C (89) °F	31.1 °C (88) °F	30.5 °C (86.8) °F	29.5 °C (85) °F	27.9 °C (82.3) °F	27.1 °C (80.9) °F	27 °C (80.5) °F	27.6 °C (81.6) °F	28.6 °C (83.6) °F	29.7 °C (85.5) °F	31 °C (87.8) °F
Precipitation / Rainfall mm (in)	39 (1.5)	54 (2.1)	100 (3.9)	145 (5.7)	231 (9.1)	302 (11.9)	227 (8.9)	155 (6.1)	204 (8)	190 (7.5)	93 (3.7)	43 (1.7)
Humidity(%)	75%	79%	82%	84%	87%	89%	88%	87%	88%	88%	86%	80%
Rainy days (d)	9	11	17	17	20	21	20	17	20	20	17	10
avg. Sun hours (hours)	8.2	7.9	7.7	7.6	7.0	5.9	5.8	5.4	5.6	6.3	6.9	8.0

Fig. 33 Showing Weather Average by Month. The month with the highest relative humidity is June (88.78 %). The month with the lowest relative humidity is January (74.56 %). The month with the highest number of rainy days is June (27.50 days). The month with the lowest number of rainy days is January (11.33 days).

4.1.3 POPULATION AND DEVELOPMENT

Ilaje-Bariga home to an estimated population of **20,000 inhabitants**. It is a slum settlement with a lot of squatters thereby making the population high. This environment suffers from a lot of vices such as the supply of the necessary social amenities that enhances day-to-day activities in the society, scattered layout plan of buildings. Consequently, this has affected negatively on the giving raise to the following;

DEMOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS

POPULATION OF BUILDINGS

TOTAL- 1269 approx.

No of residential buildings: 673 approx.

No of mixed use buildings: 266 approx.

No of commercial buildings: 63 approx.

No of institutions: 38 approx.

No of religious buildings: 140 approx.

No of green/open area: 25 approx.

Water logged area: 5%

POPULATION OF STREETS

TOTAL- 42 approx.

1.TIJANI ASHOGBON ST.

2.ASANI ST.

3.OLANREWAJU ST

4.TESLIM NOSIRU ST.

5.ILAJE RD.

6.JOLAOSHO ST.

7.ABEOKUTA ST

8.ANUOLUWAPO CL.

9.AGBE DAVIES ST.

10.MOWOWALE ST.

11.ODUSANYA ST

12.ADUNNI ST

13.BABAJIDE EWULOMI ST.

14.AYOOLA LAWAL ST

15.AWIN ST.

16.IDOWU ST

17.SHITU AFINNI CL.

18.OLOWALE ST.

19.OGUNGBAMILA ST.

20.ADEBOYE ST

21.OKUNSANYA ST.

POPULATION OF STREETS TOTAL- 42 approx.

22.OSINFOLARIN ST.

23.LATEEF FAGBEMI ST.

24.CHIEF IFEANYI ST.

25.OLAWALE AWAL ST.

26.AJILEYE ST

27.SHOKUNBI ST

28.ODELANA ST

29.OREMEJI ST

30.OBADIAH ST

31.OSENATU ST

32.ADEDOYIN OSINBAJO ST

33.PRINCE ADISA ESHLOKUN ST.

34.DENDEKE ST

35.OLATUNJI ST.

36.ALH. ALIMI ST.

37.REBECCA AIYETIWA ST

38.OGBERE ST.

39.ALHAJI ALAKE ST.

40.ADEDEJI ADEYEMI AVE

41.IFESOWAPO ST.

42.AMODU ST.

POPULATION OF RESIDENTS

NUMBER OF RESIDENCES

673 approx.

0-1 STOREY - 523 approx.

2-3 STOREY- 138 approx.

4 & ABOVE- 12 approx.

An average of 6 rooms per floor and 3 people per room.

0-1 STOREY- (523 x 6 x 3)

=9,414 residents

2-3 STOREY- (138 x 6 x 3)

=2,484 residents

4 & above- (12 x 6 x 3)

=216 residents

TOTAL NO. OF RESIDENTS

=12,114 residents

- High traffic
- Low Landscaping
- Bad house clusters
- Poor spatial distribution of commercial and industrial area
- Clusters of vehicle parked on the side of the road constraining roads
- Poor access to public transportation
- No recreation area
- Vehicle pollution

4.2 SITE SELECTION AND ANALYSIS

The Ilaje base map was produced from the first semester project on urban renewal project.

Identifying structures such as residential, commercial, religious, industrial etc using various colors. This was also made possible with the help of google maps as the Ilaje's map source.

Below shows the base map of Ilaje.

Fig. 34 Base Map

4.3 CRITERIA FOR SITE SELECTION

My reasons for the selection of my site will be based on the following:

- Location & Accessibility
- Environment
- Topography
- Size and shape
- Secure / Safe

Location; Also prior to the previous urban renewal project. Ilaje was zoned according to different activities i.e. Residential, commercial, religious, institutional, recreational, service and industrial zones. It was fitting for the site to fall under educational zone due to its purpose.

Accessible from the main road (Ilaje road). Below shows the zoned base map of Ilaje

The environment is a calm place, although its bounded by Ilaje major road. It's still calm, it is almost centrally placed in the community, which makes it a common environment people of the community will like to go to. The proposed site is also bounded by the: Oremeji street, Alhaji Alimi street, olatunji rufai street

Topography is economical as it is relatively flat, that can easily be leveled. It lacks vegetation cover or green area, but the soil has potentials for vegetation. Below shows the terrain map of Ilaje (including proposed site)

The shape of the site is not a regular type its more like a rectilinear shape, which is still good for proper site planning and arrangement. In terms of size the area cleared wasn't ambiguous, due to the fact that it is an urban area, not much luxurious space available. Its total square area is 21694.176 m².

Maximize visual access to corridors and school grounds. Control access to the building and grounds by individuals and vehicles. Use durable, non-toxic building materials.

Fig. 35 showing activities zoning

Fig. 36 Terrain map

4.4 SITE ANALYSIS

Fig. 31 Sun Path

ROAD NETWORK ANALYSIS

Fig. 32 Noise Analysis

WIND ANALYSIS

WIND ANALYSIS SHOWING THE WIND PATTERN IN A DURATION OF A YEAR, Ilaje- Bariga

Fig. 33

4.5 DESIGN BRIEF

The design of a leaning environment in an urban area for students receiving secondary education. Utilizing design element such as natural daylighting and fenestration system for better performance and visual comfort of student

4.5.1 SPACE PROGRAMMING

Problems identified and needs of the student-residents of Ilaje community

- Classroom adequate for an urban population size
- Space for sporting activities and recreation
- Adequate daylighting in classroom

4.5.2 SPACES PROVIDED

Administrative

- Principal's Office
- Vice principal's office
- Staff Room
- First-Aid Room

Laboratories & Utility

- Science Laboratory
- Music studio
- General workshop
- Toilet
- General Store

Athletics

- Volley ball court
- Basketball field
- Soccer field
- Gymnasium

Academics & Miscellaneous

- Classroom
- General Classroom
- Multipurpose Hall
- Library

4.6 DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Orientation Design Consideration

- Sun path and Wind Direction
- The placement of the building on the site and arrangement of spaces and openings – would be consider
- Large openings would not face directly to the East and West as to avoid direct sunlight and concentration of heat. The lesser surface area / or building facade exposed to the sun, lesser will be the conductive heating
- Placing openings parallel to the wind orientation to creates cool interior
- Use of wind direction so that it can be channelized through the interiors
- Consider the placement & size of openings for optimum ventilation

4.6.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Fig. 34

4.7 BUBBLE DIAGRAM

Fig. 35

4.8 ARCHITECTURAL PLANS

Design Drawings so far...

SITE PLANS

GROUND FLOOR

EAST ELEVATION

NORTH ELEVATION

SECTION 1

SECTION 2

GYMNASIUM GROUND FLOOR PLAN

GYMNASIUM ROOF PLAN

GYMNASIUM WEST ELEVATION

GYMNASIUM NORTH ELEVATION

GYMNASIUM SOUTH ELEVATION

RENDERS

Chapter 5: CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

5.1 SUMMARY

While the bulk of this research consists of three fundamental expositions, first the discussion of the concept of daylighting. Secondly, an assessment on the daylighting system and its theoretical framework. Thirdly, an analytical discussion, based on field surveys carried out on the way of life in relation to how they view recreation in the Ilaje community, (chapter 3), However, this chapter focuses on the findings of the research, its implications, the recommendations and the study's conclusion. To stimulate further research, the work areas that are yet to be explored are re-emphasized.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The present review paper has allowed light to be shed on several issues concerning daylight exploitation in educational premises, including recurrent problems, ways to measure daylight suitability for visual comfort and current trends in terms of technologies and design approaches. The first outcome is that daylight optimization in classrooms is a very complex task, where several different, and somewhat contrasting. Requisites must be met, such as sufficient and well distributed illuminance levels to accomplish the visual tasks, avoidance of glare occurrence due to direct sunlight, good spectral quality and, last but not least, possibility to integrate daylight with the contribution of dimmable and high-efficiency artificial lighting systems. Moreover, the compliance with all these requisites is complicated by the intrinsic dynamic and climate-related nature of daylight.

Ilaje community, a suburb as vibrant as this in terms of the numerous ethnicity and people, it would be perfect to add a catalyst to provide a place for people to get together and celebrate

communal harmony and togetherness. The building is designed on the theme of climate inclusion. A good deal of thought has been put into the needs of those who will come to the centre as well as those who will work in it. Looking back this thesis project involved lot of energy and time, it has been a stressful but wonderful experience.

5.3 RELEVANCE TO ARCHITECTURE

Architecture is a discipline that seeks to solve problems as regards to catering for the need of the all in the best possible way. Architecture transform these needs into concept and then develop the concept information into building images. This implies that the basic and most primary objective of architecture is to solve social and environmental problems as executed in this design thesis. This work therefore stands as a reference point of how architecture can improve student effective performance and their visual and thermal comfort

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

Several design factors such as climate, and orientation consideration expounded upon in this study (Chapter 2) should be taken into consideration

REFERENCES

1. Daryanani S. Design Consideration for the Daylighting of New Commercial Buildings. *Energy and Buildings* 1984;6: 109-118.
2. Collins B. L. Review of the Psychological Reaction to Windows. *Lighting Research and Technology* 1976;8(2):80-88.
3. Universal Basic Education Commission of Nigeria (UBE), MINIMUM STANDARDS FOR BASIC EDUCATION IN NIGERIA 2010; 7, 21
4. BAKER, N. & K. Steemers. 2002. *Daylight Design of Buildings*. James & James, London.
5. THOMAS, R. Ed. 1999. *Environmental Design: An Introduction for Architects and Engineers*. Spon Press, London
6. Hopkinson R. G., Petherbridge P., Longmore J. *Daylighting*. London: Heinemann, 1966.
7. Ander.G.D. *Daylighting Performance and Design*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold, 1995.
- 8 Moore F. *Concepts and Practice of Architectural Daylighting*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold, 1991.
9. Baker N., Fanchiotti A., Steemers K., ed. *Daylighting in Architecture: A European Reference Book*. London: James & James Ltd, 1993.

- 10 HEERWAGEN, D. 2004. Passive and Active Environmental Controls: Informing the Schematic Designing of Buildings. McGraw Hill, New York.
- 11 An Investigation of Alternative Daylight Metrics_PhD Thesis_Longyu Guan
- 12 GOULDING, J.R., J.O. Lewis, T.C. Steemers ed. 1994. Energy Conscious Design: A Primer for Architects. Batsford Limited, London
- 13 LECHNER, N. 2009. Heating, Cooling, Lighting: Sustainable Design Methods For Architects. Wiley, New Jersey.
- 14 Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory. Tips for Daylighting with Windows; 2013
- 15 J. m, F. Rubinstein, S. Selkowitz, Tips for daylighting with windows: the integrated approach, LBNL Publication 790.
- 16 M. Bodart, A. Deneyer, A. De Herde, P. Wouters, A guide for building daylight scale models, Architectural Science Review 50 (1), (2007), pp. 31-36.
17. Yeang, K. (1999), The Green Skyscraper: The basis for Designing Sustainable Intensive Buildings, Prestel Verlag, Munich, p.232.
18. AIA. (1982), Architect's Handbook of Energy Practice: Daylighting, American Institute of Architects, New York, pp.6-7
19. CIBSE. (1987), Window Design: Application Manual, Chartered Institute of Building Services Engineers, London, pp.10-31.
20. Wu, W. & Ng, E. (2002), A review of daylighting in schools, Proceedings of the Conference on Tropical Daylighting and

Building, National University of Singapore

21. Bezjak, B.; Černe, B.; Kalčič, I.; Medved, S. Optimizing the Form of School Buildings by Using the Requirements for Daylight Illumination. *Archit. Sci. Rev.* 2003, 46, 305–311.

22. DfEE (1999). *Lighting Design for Schools, Building Bulletin 90*. London, Department for Education and Employment, HMSO.

23. *Daylighting in Schools Energy Costs Reduced ... Student Performance Improved*
Michael H. Nicklas, AIA, President
Gary B. Bailey

24. CHPS (2006). *The Collaborative for High Performance Schools: Best Practice Manual*. California, The US Department of Energy, www.chps.net. accessed 10/02/2007.

25. Herbert M. Eckerlin; *An Evaluation of Daylighting in Four Schools in the Research Triangle Area of North Carolina; A Summary Report 2015*

26. Robbins, C.L. 1986. *Daylighting: Design and Analysis*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company.

27. Rubin A.I., Collins, B.L., Tibbott, R.L. 1978. Window blinds as a potential energy saver – a case study, Building Science series 112 NBS, Washington National Bureau of Standards

28. Inoue, T., Kawase, T., Ibamoto, S., Takakusa, Y., Matsuo. 1988. The development of an optimal control system for window shading devices based on investigations in office buildings. *ASHRAE Transactions* 94(2).

29. Zhang, A.; Bokel, R.; van den Dobbelsteen, A.; Sun, Y.; Huang, Q.; Zhang, Q. Optimization of thermal and daylight performance of school buildings based on a multi-objective genetic algorithm in the cold climate of China. *Energy Build.* 2017, 139, 371–384

30. Patricia Plympton Susan Conway; *Daylighting in Schools: Improving Student Performance and Health at a Price Schools Can Afford*

31. NICHOLAS WALLIMAN; *RESEARCH METHODS: THE BASICS*